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Review Article

THE ROLE OF FAMILY CARE IN MODIFYING LIFESTYLE AND METFORMIN IN PATIENTS WITH DIABETES TYPE 2

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Abstract:

Introduction: The second type of diabetes is rapidly increasing worldwide and one of the most common causes of this disease is obesity. In order to prevent the serious complications of diabetes type 2 of, health control should be given to people who are more susceptible than others to the occurrence of diabetes and its complications through in the care of the family and the regulation and modification of the lifestyle of these patients.

Objectives:

The goal of research is to know the effect of modifying the lifestyle of diabetics Type II and the same as the drug metformin to reduce blood sugar and reduce the obesity in those patients with diabetes type II and reducing the serious complications of the disease. **methods:** The study was conducted on three different groups. Each group 30 patients between the ages of 40 and 80 years old. With high blood sugar level. consisted During the five-month period, one group was treated to change lifestyle in terms of nutrition and increased physical activity. Metformin is given twice per day with 500 mg. the third group is control group. Blood glucose, body mass index, waist size and hemoglobin A1c were measured at the beginning of the test and after five months of comparison between the groups in the results. **Results:** A comparison of the three groups of blood glucose, body mass index and hemoglobin A1C showed that the metformin group had a significantly lower blood sugar level and a body mass index, whereas the second group changed the lifestyle It was also found that the blood sugar level decreased as well as haemoglobinA1C compared to the control group and this confirms that changing lifestyle and medication metformin in the presence of family care greatly reduces the level of results in blood sugar and hemoglobin A1C. **Conclusion:** Modifying the diet and increase physical movement with the treatment of metformin and lifestyle modification improves and affects the blood sugar and reduce the obesity and delay complications of the symptoms of diabetes type II

Key words: Family care, Metformin, life style, obesity and type 2 diabetes.

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INTRODUCTION

Diabetes is a disease prevalent in our time and the beginning may be caused by hereditary micro or other factors and the cause of this disease is the inability of the pancreas to produce the required amount of insulin or insulin product is ineffective, leading to disorders, the most important for diabetes is the high sugar In the blood the disease is detected by increasing blood sugar which leads to the kidneys being unable to observe the sugar and therefore sugar appears in urine analysis.(1) If high blood sugar persists for a long time without controlling the height, it will damage the blood vessels and if it continues to cause complications in the kidneys, nerves and peripheral vessels and the occurrence of complications in the retina. If this blood sugar is controlled.

Type II is the most common types and affects adults (usually over the age of forty) and this type is accompanied by other diseases such as: high blood pressure, high blood lipids, and obesity, which makes patients of this type more susceptible to atherosclerosis, The reason for this type is the lack of effective insulin produced by the body is the cause of obesity or may be due to lack of movement or the use of some drugs.

One of the main factors that help in preventing the complication of type 2 diabetes is family care ,family care in monitoring the follow up investigations of their patients and help them in modifying life style with decreasing obesity which is considered the main cause of diabetes through taking Metformin which play important role in decreasing obesity, A US study found that diabetes treatment is to support family and friends, not only at the emotional level, but also at the level of encouragement and motivation.

The study was conducted on 300 elderly and diabetic patients, studying the extent to which relatives and friends identify the patient's feelings,

and how much effort he or she makes to recover from the disease

The result was that blood sugar levels were higher in people with higher stress than those without stress, and relatives should encourage their parents to pay tribute to their efforts to treat the disease

A number of lifestyle factors play an important role in type 2 diabetes

including: obesity (defined as a BMI of over), lack of physical activity, malnutrition, stress, and urbanization

Dietary factors also affect the possibility of type2 diabetes.for example

excess consumption of sugar-sweetened beverages is associated with increased susceptibility. Fat type in the diet also plays an important role. Saturated fats cause increased susceptibility, while polyunsaturated fat and monounsaturated fat Inability to reduce the possibility of infection. Eating too much white rice also appears to play a role in increasing the likelihood of infection and it is believed that non-exercise contributes to complications in many cases

Metformin is an antihyperglycemic drug taken orally by the class of purguanide. It is the first diabetes, in particular, for treatment line for type 2 people who are overweight or obese, and who have normal renal function.(2)(3)It has been used in gestational diabetes because of safety concerns. It is also used to treat PCOS and has been tested in other diseases where insulin resistance plays an important role. Metformin works by inhibiting the production of glucose by the liver.(4)

Limited evidence suggests that metformin may prevent cardiovascular complications, and possibly

cancer complications in diabetic patients. (5) Metformin helps reduce LDL levels and triglyceride, which is not associated with high weight; in some people, weight loss is encouraged.

(6) Metformin is one of two oral hypoglycemic drugs in the WHO list of essential drugs

RESULTS:

In the start of the study in the different three groups the level of Hba1c is measured and it was high because of irregular blood sugar level. Then they are given chance to modify lifestyle with one group and taking metformin for another group. HBA1C is measured again in both groups it recorded with the first group 6.2 mmol per one litre and recorded with the second group 6.3 mmol per one litre. It meant that HBA1C decreased with both groups who change their life style and metformin under the care of their families.

BMI was measured also in the start of the study and measured again after 5 months, in the first it was very high but after modifying life style and metformin it recorded 1.3 for both groups as body weight decreased nearly 4 Kg with lifestyle modification and metformin.

Also, waist circumference decreased 2.5cm in both groups after the 5 months.

DISCUSSION:

Since many patients with type 2diabetes, and they are young people who take treatment and exercise that reduce the complications of diabetes within the family environment, it is important that the families of patients participate in improving the results of diabetes through follow-up and care and this concluded in previous studies reviewed along continuous past 20years from 1994 to 2014 have been found that there is a lot of studies that proved that family intervention for patients with type II diabetes and its role in the participation of diabetic significantly improves the incidence of complications and makes patients adhere to treatment and thus reduce the complications of serious disease like atherosclerosis of arteries and others.

Type 2diabetes can be prevented by changing the lifestyle and use of certain medications.(7) There is much evidence that if combined exercise and diet, as well as medication, for example, metformin, all of this is effective in preventing the progression of diabetes symptoms In patients with the disease and when compared with the group control and the existence of groups that change their lifestyle and treated with metformin reduced the weight of their bodies as well as the size of the waist as well as

Hba1c and body mass index has confirmed some studies that indicated that if the weight loss by 10%. (8)

During the six months, this reduces blood sugar in patients with diabetes and has excessive obesity; it is confirmed through the study of conducted in Finland, the study found that life-rate adjustments reduce the risk of diabetes complications in patients with type 2 diabetes (9). Studies have also shown that diabetes is reduced by diet and exercise by more than 40% by another study conducted in the country of China. (10)

Through the program of prevention of diabetes, some studies have shown that in the comparison between two groups, one of which have changed the lifestyle and then took metformin drug that the incidence of diabetes has decreased with this type, which deals in the lifestyle and medicines by more than 50%.(11)

Some other studies indicated that the prevention of diabetes number two told us of many complications such as atherosclerosis which is now considered one of the leading causes of death in people with Type 2 diabetes who can also be investigated in the future.(12)(13)

CONCLUSION:

One of the factors that help to reduce blood sugar levels and regulate it is to modify the lifestyle in terms of diet as well as increasing physical activity. It has been concluded that medical treatment through metformin reduces the risk of the disease. The continuous prevention against diabetes through learning the patient with diabetes and his family the benefits of modifying life styles and change it to better as well as treatment with metformin, which leads to a decrease in the incidence of vascular diseases in atherosclerosis, which is a major cause of death in patients with diabetes type II

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